

Production of Vermicompost Through Vermitechnology Using Obnoxious Weed *Argemone*

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Abstract

Argemone maxicana L. and *Argemone ochroleuca* Sweet. were subjected to earthworm species *Amyntus alexandri* for conversion of useful product the "Vermicompost" through vermitechnology. It was observed that entire organic waste of the plant species was converted into the vermicast, which was analysed chemically for various parameters. The study revealed that the vermicompost of *A.alexandri* species was rich in fertilizing qualities

Keywords Earthworm, Vermicompost.

Introduction

Argemone mexicana L. and *Argemone ochroleuca* Sweet. are noxious weeds, which cause harm to agriculture, environment and human health. Several attempts have been made for prevention, eradication and control but the results are not so promising. However, Vermitechnology is the latest aspects of biotechnology where application of earthworm is made for combating the waste disposal problem for minimising the production effect and to get useful product "Vermicompost".

Aim of study

This paper describes the production of vermicompost using these two species and their nutrient potentiality.

Review of Literature

Similar studies carried out by Biradar,D.P. (2006). Bionutrient potentiality of *Parthenium hysterophorus* and it's utility of green manure in rice ecosystem, Sharma, V.Pandher, J.K. and Kanwar, .K. (2008), Biomangement of *Lantana (Lantana camara* L.) and *Parthenium hysterophorus* L. through vermicomposting and it's response on soil fertility, Sharma,Rajeev, Dwivedi, H.S. and Dwivedi, P.(2016). Utilization of three obnoxious weeds (*Parthenium hysterophorus*, *Lantana camara* and *Eichhornia crassipes*) through vermicomposting and their response on vegetative growth of Soyabean crop , R. Ananthvalli et.al. (2019). Vermistabilization of sea weeds using an indigenous earthworm species *Perionyx excavatus*, C.Devi. et.al. (2020). Bioconversion of *Lantana camara* by vermicomposting with two different earthworm species in monoculture, H.Kauser. (2021). Fate of invasive weed *Mikania micrantha* Kunth using vermitechnology employing three monoculture of earthworm species, H.Kauser. Meena Khwairakpam(2022). Composting and vermicomposting of obnoxious weeds--A novel approach for degradation of allelochemicals.

Methodology

The pot experiment was conducted during Rainy season. To prepare suitable feeding material for earthworms for production of vermicompost, plant parts were dried and mixed with soil and cow dung. This was kept for 15-20 days for partial degradation. This partially degraded material was taken for experiment study. Seven amendments were prepared for plant material.

Table 1. Amendments of plant material for vermicompost

Experiment No.	No. Of Replicates	Ratio Plant : Soil	Weight In Gram Plant : Soil
1	03	0 : 6 (R ₁)	Nil : 600
2	03	1 : 5 (R ₂)	100 : 500
3	03	2 : 4 (R ₃)	200 : 400
4	03	3 : 3 (R ₄)	300 : 300
5	03	4 : 2 (R ₅)	400 : 200
6	03	5 : 1 (R ₆)	500 : 100
7	03	6 : 0 (R ₇)	600 : Nil

Three pots of 9 inches in diameter were taken for each amendments and 25 mature local species of earthworms. *Amyntus alexandri* were transferred in each pot and allowed to grow. Regular water supply was maintained. After three months the experiment was terminated and the cast were collected separately and analyzed for chemical analysis.

pH and electrical conductivity of worm and determined in 1:5 soil solution of fresh sample using a digital pH meter and conductivity meter following methods of Jackson(1967) for the estimation of organic matter and nitrogen, worm cast was dried to constant weight in a hot air oven at 80 degree Celsius . Total organic matter was estimated by rapid titration method of Walkely and Black (1934) using diphenylamine as an indicator. Total nitrogen was determined by macro Kjeldahl method (Piper 1942). It was proceeded by digestion (in digester Tecator 2006), (in distillation unit), and titrated using 0.1N HCl. Available phosphorus was extracted with 0.002 N Sulphuric acid after stirring soil for half hour (Hesse 1971). The total phosphorus was determined by colorimetric method employing ammonium molybdate and stannous chloride.

Table 2 :Chemical Characteristics of cast of *Amyntus alexandri* cultured on *Argemone* Organic waste in different ratios.

Material	Chemical Characteristics	Plant Material :Soil--	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7
Argemone species	pH		7.2	7.1	7.1	7.2	7.2	6.8	6.8
	Electrical Conductivity m/mhos/cm		0.57	0.64	0.79	1.04	0.88	1.74	2.82
	Total Phosphorus % in mg/litre		0.00001	0.00004	0.00003	0.00006	0.00010	0.00007	0.00008
	Total Organic Matter%		8.44	8.51	8.99	9.33	10.60	9.82	10.08
	Total Nitrogen%		0.32	0.26	0.37	0.50	0.60	0.52	0.43

Result and Discussion

The data of the analysis of vermicompost are presented in table 2. pH values in seven amendments for *Argemone* varied between 6.6 to 7.2.

Electrical conductivity was found to be in the range of 0.57m mhos/cm to 2.02mhos/cm in *Argemone*. Electrical conductivity was 0.57, 0.64, 0.79, 1.04, 0.88, 1.74,2.02mhos/ in seven amendments. Total phosphorus showed an increase / decrease pattern and varied between 0.00001 to 0.0001mg/litre%. As the values were 0.00001, 0.00004, 0.00003, 0.00006, 0.0001 and 0.00008mg/litre% for the seven amendments. The data for total organic matter (%) show an increase trend as plant material is increased in the amendments. It varied between 8.44% and 10.60% in *Argemone*. The values for seven amendments were 8.44, 8.51, 8.99, 9.33, 10.60, 9.02 and 10.08%.

The percentage of total nitrogen in seven amendments show a significant increase in the plant, it's values were 0.32, 0.26, 0.37, 0.50, 0.60, 0.52, 0.43% for *Argemone*. Introduction of various local species for production of vermicast by using various earthworm species has gained importance for the composting of various animals and plants residues under semi- natural conditions. In this context a local species, *Amyntus alexandri*, was incorporated for the production of vermicompost by using *Argemone* plant species in different ratios. After three months of study it was observed that entire waste was converted into vermicompost, which was analysed for various parameters like pH, electrical conductivity, total phosphorus, nitrogen and total organic matter. Nogales et.al. (1998) studied degradation of dry olive oil cake through *Eisenia anderi* and the product obtained after 35 days was analysed for total organic carbon, total nitrogen, total phosphorus, pH and electrical conductivity etc.

The earthworm cast contains concentrated phosphorus, exchangeable magnesium, potassium and calcium, all essential for plant growth. The enrichment of earthworm casting in having essential plant nutrients such as N,K,P,Ca and Mg has been demonstrated by several workers (Lunt & Jacobson 1944, Parle 1963, Graff 1970). The present study also indicated that the earthworm castings of the plant material was richer organic carbon, nitrogen, and total phosphorus. Earthworms provide ideal conditions for nitrogen fixing bacteria and also discharge their nitrogenous waste into vermicompost (Bhawalker, 1992). Heine & Larink (1993) measured the cast production of *Lumbricus terrestris*, and analyzed it for Ca, P, and N. The content of Ca, P, and N in the cast was higher than the same amount of food. Nainawat (1997), Khandal (1999) ,Garg and Bhardwaj (2001) found that the casts produced by decomposition of kitchen waste, garden waste, municipal waste, terrestrial waste and aquatic weeds were also richer in these components, hence, confirming the results of the study. The data also revealed that the cast produced through vermicompost helps in maintaining the pH of soil that is chemically more neutral than the surrounding soil. It is because almost all the enzymes work at ideal pH between 6.3 and 7.3, which is responsible for maintaining Ph of the vermicompost (Bhiday 1992). Similarly total phosphorus, nitrogen and organic matter were also higher. The earthworms improve soil properties, augment the amount of mobile phosphorus and potassium (Atlavinyte et.al. 1975, Graff 1972 and Sokolov 1956) and increase the yield of plants (Atlavinyte et.al. 1968, Atlavinyte 1975 and Edwards 1980).

Conclusion

Thus the present study supports the views of these researchers. This study also showed wastes through vermicomposting of *A. alexandri*, prepared with *Argemone* species organic wastes through vermicomposting process were rich in fertilizing qualities.

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